
SCHOOL CULTURAL NORMS AS PREDICTORS OF TEACHERS' JOB COMMITMENT IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract

The study examined school cultural norms as predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Three research questions guided the study and six null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study was a correlational research design. The population of the study is 6,598 teachers in the 267 public secondary schools from the six Education Zones in Anambra State. The sample of 660 teachers (that is, 10% of teachers' population) was used for the study. Multistage sampling techniques comprising of proportionate stratified and simple random sampling technique was used for the study. Two instruments were used for data collection: School Cultural Norms Questionnaire (SCNQ) and Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire (TJCQ). The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation. Face validation was done by three experts while construct validation was carried out with Principal Component Analysis approach. The reliability of the instruments was trial tested in Enugu State using Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient and the average coefficient values of 0.822 for SCNQ and 0.851 for TJCQ are considered highly reliable and suitable for the study. Simple linear regression analysis was used for the study. The study revealed that tangible support ($r = 0.584$ $p = 0.000$), recognition ($r = 0.573$ $p = 0.000$) and honest open communication ($r = 0.577$ $p = 0.000$) positively and significantly predicted teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study concluded that proper application of school cultural norms is helpful for teachers to do their work satisfactorily and committedly for the achievement of most desired quality secondary education in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that Principals should apply and sustain the usage of honest open communication by utilizing democratic and politic language, delegating duty and authority, and allowing two-way communication in the school as it would help to enhance teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Keywords: School Cultural Norms, Tangible support, Recognition, Honest open communication

Introduction

The school cultural norms are given priority because they can affect not only the commitment of teachers but also the effectiveness of teachers in the school. Hence, schools need to establish practices that guide the teachers' work behaviour. Failing to inculcate the right work values in the secondary school teachers can greatly affect their job commitment in schools.

Teachers' job commitment is their engagement in statutory obligations in the school. Onafowope *et al.* (2023) defined teachers' job commitment as the willingness of teaching staff to put their efforts and time in performing their duties. Teachers' job commitment is the state of being loyal and devoted in executing instructional responsibilities in the school. Odoh and Nwite (2022) defined teachers' job commitment as their dedication, attachment and involvement in their work or duties in order to accomplish task and achieve positive outcomes or good results. Teachers' job commitment is the dedication of teaching staff towards their duties. Contextually, teachers' job commitment is the work attitude and behaviour exhibited by teaching staff towards attainment of predetermined educational goals and objectives. In this study, teachers' job commitment was measured with the following indices. Teachers who are committed to their job are punctual to work, deliver instruction at the stipulated period, cover scheme of work and participate in school functions. Eziuzo *et al.* (2024) opined that a teacher who is committed and loyal to his or her job exhibits positive behaviours at school such as punctuality, dedication to school work, making extra time for students after school hours, implementing diverse teaching methods in the classroom and improvising instructional materials when they are not available. Committed teachers comply with professional code of conduct and maintain high level of discipline.

Teachers' job commitment in secondary schools is the strength of a teacher's identification and involvement with the teaching job. It determines whether a person will leave or remain in the teaching profession or not. Kaegon and Okere (2023) defined teachers' job commitment as a psychological state that characterizes a teacher's relationship with his or her profession, and has implications for the decision to remain involved with it. It is the emotional bond between the teacher and the school. Teachers' job commitment is regarded as a power or quality needed to approach stress and change. It includes factors such as honesty, responsibility, and tolerance for fallibility. Teachers' job commitment is of importance as it is associated with greater job effort and involvement, that is, committed employees are less likely to leave their position and display other withdrawal behaviour such as absenteeism. The strength of any profession depends upon the degree of commitment of its members. Thus, teachers' job commitment is the strength of teachers' identification with and involvement in the school organization. It can be viewed as the dedication that teachers believe or perceive towards particular work and the job they carry out in the school. Obiekwe *et al.* (2024) described job commitment as total organism direction involving not only the conscious mind but the whole direction which is gradually achieved by the individual through a close relationship in which even unconscious tendencies are as much respected as conscious choices. Obiekwe *et al.* further noted that commitment in job is a state of attachment that defines the relationship between an actor (an individual, a group or organization) and an entity (commitment target). They disclosed that the determinants of organizational commitment include; strong desire to stay in the organization, acceptance of the organization's values, and willingness to work hard to achieve organizational goals.

The researchers defined teachers' job commitment as the feeling of dedication among teachers toward their job. This commitment area involves two essential components namely

pride in one being in the teaching job and a strong desire for professional development. In fact, after joining the profession, teachers should fully understand as long as they are there, that they have to develop pride knowing that this is a noble job charged with great responsibilities as the society hands over its students to this system for their wholesome education. In order to ensure teachers' job commitment, school cultural norms must be conducive and attractive. School cultural norms become one of the vital components in the schools that determine job commitment of teachers. Teachers are attracted to schools that have values that are perceived as being similar to their own values and this has been shown to have an effect on variables like teachers' performance and job commitment (Sibomana & Andala, 2024). It is therefore important for every school to understand their own school cultural norms so that the management can use the knowledge to wield greater control over the school.

School cultural norms are the shared values, beliefs and assumptions that exist among teachers within the school that help guide and coordinate behaviour. School norms are further defined as the traditions, beliefs, policies and norms within a school that can be shaped, enhanced and maintained through the school's principal and teachers. Within an organisational setting, school norms are perceived to be pervasive and powerful (Ahmed, 2024). For business, it has been found to be the glue that can bond employees to an organisation, and helps in achieving organisational objectives or what drives employees away.

School cultural norms are teaching and learning approaches, behaviours and relationships among or across the individuals in a school. Odoh and Nwite (2022) opined that school norms are set of values that help staff in school to understand which actions are considered acceptable and which are considered unacceptable. These are specific collection of values and norms that are shared by people and groups in the organization, control the way they interact with each other and with stakeholders outside the organization. School norms are both written and unwritten rules, laws, regulations, traditions and expectations that inform the teachers and school administrators how they are expected to behave toward each other and the teaching and learning materials they use in schools.

The school wide norms are the foundation for respectful behaviour among all in the school community. They provide an underground flow of feelings and pave the way within the school, inform of vision, values, beliefs and expectations. They are important tools that provide or hinder the change in the school cultural structure as well as the achievement of the school set goals. School norms are not merely established and published handbooks, but are nurtured by education managers and school administrators in order to create a positive effect on teachers and teaching learning situation. Saphier and King in 1985 identified twelve school norms that can impact positively on the performance and commitment of teachers. These include: collegiality, experimentation, high expectations, trust and confidence, tangible support, reaching out to the knowledge bases, appreciation and recognition, caring, celebration and humour, involvement in decision-making, protection of what is important, tradition and honest open communication.

This study focused on three of the twelve school norms identified by Saphier and King (1985); tangible support, recognition and honest open communication. The choice of these norms was based firstly on their relevance to the school setting in the study area. It is expected that if they are properly applied and enhanced in the administrative process of public secondary schools in Anambra State, they would likely impact greatly on teachers' job

commitment which would gradually translate to effective education. Secondly, given that education is fast transforming, hence a paradigm shifts from school administrators being the central focus of everyday business of school life, it is expected that the selected three school norms which are core to the cultural setting and education dynamics will boost job commitment among teachers.

It is common place to have teachers at secondary school level faced with similar needs and challenges but basically with different knowledge, ability and talents. For tangible support to thrive and impact on teachers' job commitment, the school ethics will be conducive for teachers to express a shared vision that will enable them to succeed. Teachers will not be afraid to bring up their personal problems because they know that others are on their side. They are sure that their colleagues can offer excellent ideas that will help solve their problems. Teachers found here feel so free to learn from others who are better in what they do. Odo and Nwite (2022) stated that acquiring teachers' support services, developing their skills, motivating them to high levels of performance and ensuring that they continue to maintain their commitment to the organization are essential to achieving school organizational objectives. Tangible support is associated with the general improvement of teachers in terms of attitude to work, behaviour, skills, improved job commitment and recognition.

Recognition occurs when school principals or authorities share teachers' good work and performance with them and even with extended audience. Obionu *et al.* (2024) noted that appreciation and recognition are good indications that the behaviour of the teacher is valued. They further observed that it is common in a workplace for employers to get more of the employers' behaviour they recognise and appreciate. They make teachers to fulfill task and their dreams. They are capable of eliciting good work performance needed to maintain commitment in the school. A principal's quick feedback after observing a teacher teach good lesson, after assessing his/her school records or consistently being punctual to school, will help school administrators maintain what can be described as "psychological contract". Teachers' recognitions can be as candid as a pat-on-the-back and a genuine compliment. It can also be as simple as a 'thank you', praises, applause or a friendly greeting at work (Onafowo *et al.*, 2023).

Honesty is probity and it comes with reliability and openness. Here teachers feel free to speak plainly, tactfully and directly to colleagues, parents, school principals and to their employers what they think and see about the school without fear of losing their esteem or damaging relationship. Effective teacher to teacher communication is essential to their success as teachers. Teachers need to regularly collaborate and have team planning sessions. Likewise, effective communication which underpins the knowledge, skills, and dispositions school principals require to have direct and indirect influence on teachers (Eziuzo *et al.*, 2024). In the words of Obadimeji and Oredein (2022), honest and open communication is important for school teachers to have peers to lean on during rough times, instead of finding themselves in isolation and/or always having conflict with school authority and fellow members.

These school norms work together to create effective school climate for change. Without motivated workforce, an organization could lose all that they have earned over the years. The implication of non-commitment to duty and the high rate of teacher attrition arising from poor job commitment have drawn increased attention from an array of perspective including education ministries and general society. Though seldom articulated,

the interest in these trends centres on their consequences for the students. Job commitment of teachers has direct implications on the learners and the overall success of school as an organization. Within the Nigerian contemporary society, the education of youth is an issue of serious concern because it does not only ensure sustainable development but also makes for continued capacity building. While also the current argument on whether work ethics trait and school cultural norms predict job commitment of teachers appear to be quite logical and coherent, it must also be appreciated that the argument is not backed up by empirical research data.

Furthermore, there is a growing concern in society that some principals have been found wanting in their task of administration of the school and its resources, including the teachers. Perhaps, this is due to inadequate school cultural norms which could jeopardize the commitment of teachers to the educational system. Some of these inadequacies in the area of school cultural norms like lack of tangible support, poor communication system, lack of recognition and appreciation among others. The absence of commitment on the part of the teachers has been seen as an explanation for a variety of ills, among which is absenteeism, negative work attitude, irregularities in the classroom and indiscipline among teachers. The above does not give room for collaboration between the principals and the teachers, and the adverse effect of this is on the students. As such how school cultural norms predict job commitment of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State is still in doubt and requires very urgent research attention.

Statement of the Problem

The scenarios of some teachers sneaking out of school during official hours to attend to their personal affairs, presenting ill-prepared lessons, exhibiting of poor role models to students, absenting from school and classes makes one wonders if they are committed to their job in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The unethical and uncommitted attitude of teachers towards their job may be attributed to the existence of conflict, indiscipline, poor record management, low rapport, and ill-motivation of teachers in public secondary schools in the state. The incessant cases of failure of teachers to effectively execute tasks assigned to them could be traceable to poor delegation of duties approaches of public secondary school principals in Anambra State. Teachers' adherence to professional ethics, work attitude and school norms in public secondary schools are shaped by their irrespective rules and regulations. Public secondary schools have varied rules and procedures for taking disciplinary action which could account for dissimilarity in the punctuality, absenteeism and habitual lateness to work among teachers in public secondary schools. Despite all the rules and regulations in public secondary schools, there are still traces of poor job commitment among teachers; could this be traceable to school cultural norms in the school? It is against this backdrop that this study was conceived by the researchers to determine school cultural norms as predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine school cultural norms as predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to determine how:

1. Tangible support predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Recognition predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

3. Honest open communication predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the predictive value of tangible support on teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. How does recognition predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. What is the predictive value of open communication on teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Tangible support does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Recognition does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Honest open communication does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Methods

The study adopted a correlational research design. The study was carried out in Anambra State, Nigeria. Anambra State is one of the five States in South-East, Nigeria. The population of 6,598 teachers in the 267 public secondary schools from the six education zones in Anambra State was used for the study. The sample of 660 teachers was used for the study. Multistage sampling techniques comprising of proportionate stratified and simple random sampling technique was used for the study. Two researchers structured instruments were used for data collection: School Cultural Norms Questionnaire (SCNQ) and Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire (TJCQ). The instruments are structured in three sections namely A, B and C Section A deals with the personal data of the respondents, while sections B and C deals with SCNQ and TJCQ.

School Cultural Norms Questionnaire (SCNQ) as structured by the researcher measured the prevailing school cultural norms in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The instrument SCNQ contained 30-items spread across three Clusters 'A-C.' Cluster 'A' elicited information on tangible support with 10-items; Cluster 'B' elicited information on recognition with 10-items; and Cluster 'C' elicited information on honest open communication with 10-items. These items were placed on 4-point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The range of scores was weighted as 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire (TJSQ) as structured by the researcher measured job commitment of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The instrument TJCQ has 20-items with a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA) (4 points), Agree (A) (3 points), Disagree (D) (2 points) and Strongly Disagree (SD) (1 point).

The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation. Face validation was done by three experts, two in Educational Management and one in Measurement and Evaluation, all in the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus Nigeria. On the other

hand, construct validation was carried out with the help SPSS v.25. Construct validity of the instruments for work ethics, school cultural norms and teachers' job commitment components loading seven factors was explored using Principal Component Analysis approach. The instruments were trial-tested in a single administration on a representative sample of 30 teachers randomly selected from five public secondary schools in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State. The instruments were administered to the respondents by the researchers with the help of six research assistants. Simple linear regression analysis was used to answer the research questions and test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. This statistical tool was used because the study tends to predict between quantitative independent variables and quantitative dependent variables. Often, the objective is to predict the value of an output variable (or response) based on the value of an input (or predictor) variable. The data collected was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.

For Regression Coefficient (r)

- + Sign = Positive Prediction
- Sign = Negative Prediction

The negative sign means a negative coefficient which indicates a negative prediction or correlation between variables, while a positive sign means a positive coefficient which indicates a positive prediction or correlation between variables.

For Sig. (2-tailed) when

- Sig. (2-tailed) < .05: Reject H_0 and Accept H_1
- Sig. (2-tailed) > .05: Do not reject H_0

In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if p-value is equal to or less (\leq) than significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected, but if p-value is greater than ($>$), the significant value of 0.05 the null hypotheses was accepted.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the predictive value of tangible support on teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Summary of simple regression analysis with tangible support as it predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized
	β	B	B
Constant	27.471	6.315	
Tangible Support	.592	.339	.584
R	.584		
R ²	.532		
Adj. R ²	.477		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 1 indicated that tangible support positively predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient (R = 0.584). The coefficient of determination (R²) value of 0.532 showed that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 53% of the variations in teachers' job commitment in

public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in teachers' tangible support. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of .477 indicating that 48% of the total variation in the dependent variable (teachers' job commitment) was explained by the independent variable (teachers' tangible support). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of teachers' tangible support is moderately strong in determining the teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. However, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.584$) showed that teachers' tangible support is a positive predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit increase in teachers' tangible support led to 0.584(58%) increase in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the positive prediction of teachers' tangible support on teachers' job commitment means that teachers' job commitment moderately depends on the good practices of teachers' tangible support in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: How does recognition predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Summary of simple regression analysis with recognition as it predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. B	Standardized B
Constant	26.521	7.563	
Recognition	.586	.327	.573
R	.573		
R^2	.509		
Adj. R^2	.489		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 2 indicated that recognition positively predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.573$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.509 showed that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 51% of the variations in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in teachers' recognition. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.489 indicating that 49% of the total variation in the dependent variable (teachers' job commitment) was explained by the independent variable (teachers' recognition). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of teachers' recognition is moderately strong in determining the teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Again, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.573$) showed that teachers' recognition is a positive predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit improvement in teachers' recognition led to 0.573(57%) improvement in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the positive prediction of teachers' recognition on teachers' job commitment means that teachers' job commitment moderately depends on enhanced practices of teachers' recognition and appreciation in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 3: What is the predictive value of honest open communication on teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 3: Summary of simple regression analysis with honest open communication as it predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized B
Constant	31.541	6.493	
Honest Open Communication	.594	.357	.577
R	.577		
R ²	.495		
Adj. R ²	.462		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 3 indicated that honest open communication positively predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.577$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.495 showed that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 50% of the variations in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in honest open communication. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.462 indicating that 46% of the total variation in the dependent variable (teachers' job commitment) was explained by the independent variable (honest open communication). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of honest open communication is moderately strong in determining the teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. In the same vein, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.577$) showed that honest open communication is a positive predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit increment in honest open communication led to 0.577 (58%) increment in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the positive prediction of honest open communication on teachers' job commitment means that teachers' job commitment moderately depends on the practical application of honest open communication in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

H₀₁: Tangible support does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Test of significance of simple regression analysis with tangible support does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. B	Standardized β	t- value	p- value
Constant	27.471	6.315		24.725	.000
Tangible Support	.592	.339	.584	20.664	.000
R	.584				
R ²	.532				
Adj. R ²	.477				
F	31.427				.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 4 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.584 while the R^2 is 0.532 and Adjust R^2 is 0.477. The F-ratio associated with regression is 31.427, the t-test is 20.664 and

the P-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that tangible support does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that tangible support significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

H₀₂: Recognition does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 5: Test of significance of simple regression analysis with recognition does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. B	Standardized β	t- value	p- value
Constant	26.521	7.563		22.544	.000
Recognition	.586	.327	.573	19.369	.000
R	.573				
R ²	.509				
Adj. R ²	.486				
F	29.734				.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 5 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.573 while the R² is 0.509 and Adjust R² is 0.486. The F-ratio associated with regression is 29.734, the t-test is 19.369 and the P-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that recognition does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that recognition significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

H₀₃: Honest open communication does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 6: Test of significance of simple regression analysis with honest open communication does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. B	Standardized β	t- value	p- value
Constant	31.541	5.112		26.224	.000
Honest Open Communication	.594	.357	.577	23.108	.000
R	.577				
R ²	.495				
Adj. R ²	.462				
F	34.286				.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 6 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.577 while the R² is 0.495 and Adjust R² is 0.462. The F-ratio associated with regression is 34.286, the t-test is 23.108 and the P-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05,

the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that honest open communication does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that honest open communication significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion of the Findings

Findings on how tangible support predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State showed that tangible support positively and significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The finding is as a result of the fact that tangible support to teachers is sources of motivation that drive teachers to be committed to their job in the schools. When the teachers are not adequately motivated through tangible support, it affects other aspects of the teachers' life. Thus, the findings showed that teachers' tangible support influencing teachers' job commitment were prevailing in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding agrees with Odoh and Nwite (2022) that, in most secondary schools, teachers are subjected to work under conditions where there are few or no office facilities, where classrooms are overcrowded, where promotion, payment of salaries and other entitlements are unduly delayed and motivation inadequate. This situation affects teachers' morale and the resultant effect is lack of commitment to work. Supporting this finding, Obi and Ebelechukwu (2024) discovered that teachers' motivation emerged as most powerful predictor of school climatic conditions which have shown that teachers can only put in their best and be committed to their school when their needs are satisfied and they are motivated. In the same vein, Agah and Yakubu (2024) confirmed that non-payment of fringe benefits such as health protection and retirement benefits have negative impact on teachers' job commitment. Non-payment of leave bonus and lack of incentives for teachers reduce their moral and make them reluctant to their work. This implies that non-payment of leave bonus and other incentives affects teachers' attitude to work.

Findings on how recognition predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State showed that recognition positively and significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The finding is an indication that principals in public secondary schools in Anambra State use constant words of encouragement, applaud teachers who attain higher job engagement, issue letter of commendations, bonuses and handshake to teachers to enhance their job commitment. The positive and significant prediction of recognition on teachers' job commitment is possibly due to the fact that it is means of boosting the morale of teachers to work harder for overall success of the school. This finding lends credence to the findings of Dashwep and Macha (2022) that the motivation of teachers makes them feel supported and appreciated which induce high level of job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Similarly, Ikedimma and Okorji (2023) averred that teachers are more productive, satisfied with their job and healthier, physically, emotionally, socially, and academically, when motivated by either words of praise for their contributions in the school or being recognized by the school principal through gifts and words of encouragement. In line with this, Agah and Yakubu (2024) indicated that recognition is a strong force that motivates staff for improved job commitment in schools. When teachers are recognized, they feel appreciated and valued for their contributions. It is a sign that they are doing something right, and that their efforts are being noticed. In the workplace, recognition can come in many forms, from formal awards or bonuses to more informal gestures like a 'good job' ping from a principal or colleague. Whatever form it takes, recognition is a powerful tool that can boost teachers' morale, motivation, commitment and performance in schools.

Findings on how honest open communication predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State showed that honest open communication positively and significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The finding revealed that principals in public secondary schools in Anambra State listen attentively to teachers during interaction, speak clearly to the understanding of staff, make use of right choice of words during conversation with staff, ask pertinent questions while interacting with teachers, make use of eye contacts while discussing with teachers and successfully disseminate information to teachers through electronic devices. This finding could be explained by the fact that principals rely on communication to instruct, direct and guide the activities of teachers to aid and improve teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The effectiveness of principals on communication contributes to teachers' job commitment by disseminating information about exact tasks which are required of teachers, how and when to execute the tasks. The findings of the study agreed with Eziuzo *et al.* (2024) that poor principals' competencies in the areas of planning, communication and delegation prevent effective job commitment by teachers. Principals are required to communicate their ideas and plans about their school programmes to teachers to enable them to undertake their job effectively. A two-way communication system is required for both principals and teachers to facilitate teachers' job commitment in school. Obiekwe *et al.* (2024) admitted that, through an effective communication system in school, teachers would be able to express themselves to the principals about their job assignments, working conditions and concerns regarding their professional growth. Communication is part of the principals' administrative skill to establish a sound information network that keeps teachers informed about the progress and challenges facing a school.

Conclusion

The study has shown that school cultural norms is pervasive and powerful. For schools, they are forces for positive change or definite barriers for the desired change. For teachers, it is either the glue that bonds them to the school or what drives them away. The study concluded that proper application of school cultural norms is helpful for teachers to do their work satisfactorily and committedly for the achievement of most desired quality secondary education in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Recommendations

1. The state government should make the teaching profession more desirable by ensuring the full payment of teachers' job benefits and the provision of facilities in the school. This will improve teachers' attitude to work.
2. The Post Primary Schools Service Commission in conjunction with Secondary school principals should constantly motivate teachers by giving out awards and recognitions to high performing teachers.
3. Principals should apply and sustain the usage of honest open communication by utilizing democratic and politic language, delegating duty and authority, and allowing two-way communication in the school as it would help to enhance teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

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